

STUDY ON THE CORE-SHELL STRUCTURED FIBER TYPE STRAIN SENSOR WITH LOAD BEARING CHARACTERISTICS IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, core-shell structured strain sensors with a sandwich structured conductive layer, which have high load carrying capacity as well as high sensing performances were fabricated by using a dry-jet wet spinning system. The core part of the fiber sensor was made of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) which has high modulus and strength. The shell parts of the fiber sensor as an electrically conductive layer were composed with the sandwich structured MWCNT conductive coating layers to enhance the sensing performances. An outer surface of the fiber sensor was coated with a thin polyurethane (PU) layer for the electrical insulation. The scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to confirm the formation of the core-shell structure of the fiber sensor. Single filament tensile tests were performed to estimate the mechanical properties of the fiber sensors. Strain sensitivity and repeatability of the fiber sensors were measured using an LCR meter during a static and dynamic tensile test, respectively. From the results, we confirmed that the core-shell structured sensor fibers with sandwich structured MWCNT layer showed significantly enhanced the mechanical properties by controlling the drawing condition and sensing performances including sensitivity and linearity by controlling structural configuration of the conductive layers as well.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the years, foil-type strain gauges and fiber bragg grating (FBG) sensors have been commonly used for health monitoring of composite structures through strain measurements. The metallic foil-type strain gauges have high strain sensitivity (Gauge factor $\cong 2$) but they cannot be embedded into the composite materials. In addition, too many sensor nodes are required to detect a small crack or delamination in the whole area of the composites. On the other hand, FBG sensors can be embedded in the composite, which enables them to measure strain distribution in the composite [1, 2]. However, FBG sensors can act as defects in the composite materials because they have much lower mechanical properties than the reinforcing fibers and they are vulnerable to the impact load due to the intrinsic brittle characteristic originated from the quartz or silica core part. Moreover, the diameter of the commonly used FBG sensors is larger than the thickness of a single ply of woven fabrics or prepregs, which results in stress concentration at the interface between the sensor and the matrix.

In this work, core-shell structured strain sensors with a sandwich structured conductive layer were fabricated by using a dry-jet wet spinning system to enhance the load carrying capacity as well as high sensing performances. The dry-jet spun ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fiber were post-treated including hot-stretching process and acid surface treatment to improve the tensile properties and the interfacial strength with the shell part, respectively. The shell part of the sensor fiber including Polyurethane (PU) and sandwich structured CNT layer was formed on the core fiber by dip coating method. The morphologies of the sensor fibers was observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The mechanical properties of the prepared sensor fibers were measured by tensile tests with respect to the post-treatment conditions. The sensitivity of the sensor fibers were measured using LCR meter during static tensile tests.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Dry-jet wet spinning of UHMWPE fibers

UHMWPE powders (U050: Average molecular weight 5×10^6 g/mol, Korea Petrochemical Ind. Co. Ltd., Republic of Korea) were simply mixed with paraffine oil (Sigma-Aldrich Inc., USA) and kept in a $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during 24 h for the swelling process to enhance chain mobility of the UHMWPE in the subsequent dissolving process. Swelled UHMWPE powders were dissolved in paraffin oil at $170\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h to prepare a solution at 4 wt.% and kept in a spinning solution syringe at $170\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h to stabilize the molecular chains of the UHMWPE solution.

Figure 1: Dry-jet wet spinning system.

A UHMWPE core fiber was spun with the prepared spinning dope by using a dry-jet wet spinning method at a lab-scale spinning instrument (Wet spinning system, DISSOL, Republic of Korea) as shown in Fig. 1. A spinneret which has a single circular cross section hole nozzle with a diameter of 0.65 mm was equipped in the spinning system. The UHMWPE spinning solution was fed to the spinneret with 0.2 MPa of N_2 gas pressure that used to prevent thermal degradation of UHMWPE solutions and extrude from the spinneret uniformly. The air gap between the spinneret and the coagulation bath was set to 5 cm for the increase of molecular chain alignment in the longitudinal direction of the fiber. The UHMWPE fiber was formed by solidification of the polymer solution extruded from the spinneret when extruding vertically into a coagulation bath containing distilled water at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Subsequently, the coagulated fiber was passed through the washing bath to remove the paraffine oil. After the wind up of initial fiber, residual paraffine oil in the fiber was removed in hexane (Sigma-Aldrich Inc., USA) for 24 h at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and rinsing process was performed to remove residual hexane in the fiber using distilled water.

2.2 Dip coating processes

Fig. 2(a) shows the schematic configuration of the sensor fiber which was composed of the following sequence: UHMWPE core fiber, 1st PU layer, MWCNT conductive layer for strain sensing, 2nd PU layer for protecting the conductive layer from dust, moisture, and other environmental factors. Figure 2(b) shows the dip coating procedure of the sensor fibers. At first, the UHMWPE fiber was submerged into the aqueous PU solution (CRP 26301, T&L Co., Ltd., Republic of Korea) and it was withdrawn from the bath after 20 sec. Subsequently, the PU coated fiber was dried at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 min and this process was repeated in 3-times. Thereafter, the electrically conductive layer was formed on the PU coated UHMWPE fiber by using the same method with the aqueous MWCNT solution (K-Nanos 100P, Kumho petrochemical Co., Ltd., Republic of Korea). In the case of the sandwich-structured conductive layer to improve sensitivity and linearity from the combination of varying concentration of MWCNT, the same coating procedures were adopted from the bottom layer of 3 wt.% MWCNT, the middle layer of 2 wt.% MWCNT, and the top layer of 3 wt.% MWCNT, respectively.

The thickness of each coating layers was determined by controlling the number of the dip coating process. Subsequently, the conductive layer coated UHMWPE fiber was dried in a 60 °C oven for 1 hour to remove excessive water in the MWCNT layer. Lastly, 2nd PU layer was coated with the same procedure of the 1st PU layer. Each specimens were named with respect to the MWCNT layer coating sequence as listed in Table 1.

Specimen naming	MWCNT layer structure
M1	Mono layer: 2 wt.%
M2	Mono layer: 3 wt.%
S1	Sandwich structure: 3 wt.% / 2 wt.% / 3 wt.%

Table 1: Specimen naming.

2.3 Tensile testing of the sensor fibers

Tensile tests were performed to investigate the mechanical properties of the sensor fibers based on the ASTM standard [3]. The configuration of the specimens were detailed in Fig. 3 (a). The prepared sensor fiber was attached on the thin paper board by epoxy adhesive (Araldite AW106, Huntsman Co., Ltd., USA) to align the single filament and control the gauge length. The tensile tests were performed using a universal testing machine (5969, INSTRON, USA) with a 5-N load cell. At least 7 test specimens were prepared and tested for each treatment condition and the results were averaged.

Figure 2: Configuration of sensor fiber with sandwich structured MWCNT layer; (a) structure of sensor fiber, (b) dip-coating procedure

2.4 Characterization of the sensor fibers

Figure 3: Schematic configurations; (a) tensile test specimens, (b) specimens for sensor property measurement.

Surface morphologies of the chromic acid treated UHMWPE core fibers and the MWCNT coated fibers were observed by using SEM (AIS 1800 C, Seron Technologies Inc., Republic of Korea). The coating thickness of MWCNT layer was also measured with respect to the number of dip coating.

The strain sensitivity was measured at the static tensile loading condition using a specimen shown in Figure 3(b). The 2nd PU layer of the prepared sensor fiber near the epoxy adhesive fixation was partially removed using acetone to connect the electrodes and the MWCNT conductive layer. The initial resistance and the resistance change of the sensor fiber at the static tensile loading were measured using a LCR meter (E4980AL, Keysight Inc., USA) with 10 Hz sampling rate. The strain sensitivity was calculated by following equation:

$$\text{Strain sensitivity} = (\Delta R / R_0) / \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where

R_0 = initial electrical resistance before applying tensile load

ΔR = change of electrical resistance against tensile strain

ε = tensile strain

From the curve fitting result of strain versus strain sensitivity curve, gauge factor (GF) was calculated over two strain ranges (1~2%, and 3~4% strain range) to investigate the linearity of strain sensitivity and fitting error was also calculated to compare with GF of 1~2% and 3~4% strain ranges.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the DSC analysis results of the as-spun UHMWPE fibers. From the results, the crystallization and melting temperatures of the as-spun fiber were approximately checked as 119 and 133 °C, respectively. Near the melting point of the UHMWPE fiber, mobility of polymer chain is improved [4]. In this case, amorphous region of the fibers can be easily transferred to crystalline under external force and temperature. In addition, when the heated fibers are cooled to near the crystallization temperature, the re-crystallization was proceeded of the amorphous regions as well as

the crystalline regions. This phenomenon can result in the enhancement of mechanical properties of the UHMWPE fibers due to increased crystallinity and chain alignment.

Figure 4: DSC measurement results of as-spun UHMWPE fibers.

Figure 5 shows the summarized mechanical properties of the UHMWPE core fibers with respect to stretching ratio and hot stretching temperature. The tensile strength and modulus of the core fibers were enhanced as the stretching ratio and hot stretching temperature was increased because the crystallinity of the core fiber increased by the rearrangement or reorientation of the molecular chains during hot-stretching process. Especially, the maximum tensile strength and modulus were shown at the highest treating temperature. This phenomenon was explained by thermal analysis results in Fig. 4 of as-spun fibers.

Figure 5: Mechanical properties of UHMWPE fibers; (a) tensile strength, (b) tensile modulus.

Figure 6(a) illustrates the surface morphologies of coated fiber with respect to the coating sequence. From the observation results, MWCNT coating layer was uniformly formed on the fibers by dip coating method. The thickness of MWCNT coating layer was steadily controlled of 4 μm with varying number of dip coatings. The electrical resistance measurement results of sensor fibers shown in Fig. 6(b). Electrical resistance was related to concentration of MWCNT layers. The electrical resistance was decreased because the electrical path of M2 was densely formed to compared with M1. Dense electrical network has the increased number of electrical path that the electrons can easily travel [5]. Consequently, high weight concentration specimen has low electrical resistance value. In particular,

the resistance value of sandwich structured MWCNT layer specimen shows the moderate results between M1 and M2 due to the combination of low and high concentration layers.

Figure 6: Surface morphologies and electrical resistance; (a) coating thickness of MWCNT layers and surface morphologies, (b) electrical resistance of sensor fibers.

The sensitivity measurement results of prepared sensor fiber during static tensile loading shown in Fig. 7. The increasing tendency of sensitivity shown all cases because the resistance changes of conductive layer were occurred by breakage of conductive network due to the tensile loading. When the applied external tensile load on the sensors, relative distance of MWCNTs become larger. Thus, the total electrical resistance increased by disconnection of MWCNT networks. From Fig. 7(a) shows the highest sensitivity and non-linear form because of the low concentration of MWCNTs. When the concentration of the MWCNT layer was low, the tunneling effect was more dominant than the direct contact of the MWCNT in the formation of the electrical path, so this phenomenon occurred. If one of the electrical paths broken by external load, total resistance of conductive layer was rapidly increased. It made sensitive sensor, however, it has problems of unstable sensing response by weak electrical path. The non-linear behaviors of specimen (a) should be caused by the non-linear relationship between the distance changes of MWCNTs and the tunneling resistance [6, 7].

Figure 7: Measurement results of strain sensitivity; (a) M1, (b) M2, (c) S1.

GF fitting results of specimen (a) also confirmed that the non-linear behavior of that sensor. GF value at the 3~4% strain dramatically increased over the 161% than 1~2% strain range. In the case of the specimen (b), linearity of the sensitivity curve was improved than the (a) owing to the increment of MWCNT concentration. From the gauge factor fitting results, GF of the specimen (b) increased over the 50% than 1~2% strain range. (b) showed the stable response with low noise level than (a) because increased MWCNT contents increased numbers of electrical path. Thus, maximum sensitivity decreased by 55% to compared with (a). Based on the sensitivity measurement results of fiber sensors with mono-MWCNT layer structure, we confirmed that the enhancement of linearity of sensing response was limited using mono-layer structures. Linear response of the strain sensor is important for accurate strain sensing, signal processing and use [8]. Thus, in this work, the sandwich structure MWCNT layer introduced for enhancing the linearity of sensing response. From the measurement results of the sensor fiber with the sandwich structured MWCNT layer as shown in (c), the effect of the combination of the different concentrations of the MWCNT layer for improving the linear sensing response can be confirmed. Sandwich structured MWCNT layer was connected in parallel between each layer. It made interesting relation between sensitive layer and stable layer, such as stable layer was compensated of non-linearity and noise level of sensitive layer, and sensitive layer was improved for strain sensitivity of sandwich structured sensing layer. In addition, the sensitivity of the developed sensor fiber was 55% higher than that of the metal foil type strain gauge and 3 times higher than that of FBG sensor.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, Load bearing strain sensor fiber with linear response, less noise level, and repeatability was fabricated using UHMWPE core fiber and sandwich structured MWCNT coating layers. The effects of sandwich structured MWCNT layer on the stable sensor response were investigated by static tensile test. Based on the results the following conclusions were obtained.

- (a) Through the analysis of melting point and crystallization temperature using DSC, the optimum hot-stretching conditions of as-spun UHMWPE fibers were confirmed.
- (b) The tensile test results of post-treated UHMWPE core fiber showed enhanced mechanical properties of sensor fibers. The tensile strength and modulus of hot-stretched sensor fiber increased by 20 times and 132 times, respectively.
- (c) The static strain sensitivity measurement result shown that sandwich structured MWCNT layer can enhance linearity of sensing response. From the GF fitting results, fitting error of GF decreased from 161% to less than 1%.

This study demonstrated that sandwich structured MWCNT coating layer with UHMWPE core fiber showed enhancement of mechanical properties of sensors and superior sensing durability.

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